

Cyclic Re-Ignition Phenomena in Pressure-Gain Constant Volume Combustors

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1. Context and objectives

Alternative combustion cycles such as Pressure-Gain Combustion (PGC) are promising avenues for decreasing both fuel consumption and pollutant emissions [1], [2]. Constant Volume Combustion (CVC) is a conventional PGC technology widely used in piston engines. Pistonless solutions are currently investigated, leveraging the constant volume combustion with a reduced mechanical complexity adapted to aircraft engine [3]. In pistonless chambers, mixing and scavenging are mostly driven by aerodynamics, and the absence of the piston yields a large aerodynamic structure that can prevent ignition. In low-scavenging configurations, long residence time areas where the fuel-air-residual burnt gas mixture can form yielding an uncontrolled cycle-to-cycle re-ignition phenomenon [4],[5],[6]. Higher cycle frequencies are required to achieve flight viable power density but the resulting aerodynamics might be incompatible with conventional spark-ignition strategies [7]. This study examines the conditions for cyclic re-ignition (RI) using liquid n-heptane under conditions typical of low compression ratio air-breathing systems. Initially, spark ignition is employed to establish a baseline scenario. Under the explored conditions, a hybrid operational point is identified where re-ignition consistently occurs after the exhaust phase of a spark-ignited cycle.

2. Experimental setup and diagnostics

CV2 is engineered to replicate the cyclic conditions and mass flow rates representative of expected combustors. Its modular design accommodates different canonical geometrical configurations as outlined in multiple patents [8], [9]. RI events are influenced by the transient mixing between RBG, directly injected fuel and separately admitted air. The aerodynamics are highly dependent on the geometrical configuration [10] which might vary based on final integration choices as seen on various patents [8], [9]. Examples of possible geometries [8], [9] are provided on Figure 1.

Figure 1 Concept view of the integration of a turboshaft engine with 10 CVC chambers (left, adapted from [9]) and chamber configuration with burnt gas transfer ports (middle, adapted from [11]). Right: CV2 combustor

In CV2, we focus on a single chamber, which can be integrated into a multichambered configuration, to understand the physics inside the chamber. The CV2 set up includes an intake and exhaust system of finite volume and operates over a finite number of cycles, typically 10 to 20. This enables accurate measurement of the mass of air injected in each cycle and control of the exhaust back pressure, which remains relatively constant across all cycles. For the purpose of this study, the chamber is set in a linear configuration that has been thoroughly characterized through PIV, infrared imaging and modelled in previous studies [11]. The sequential phases of the CVC cycle consist of the intake, combustion and exhaust. The air intake tank and exhaust tank are connected to the

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combustion chamber via fast electrical solenoid valves (COAX MK10). Hence, the leakage during the isochoric phase is negligible [6]. The combustion chamber subsystems consist of a direct fuel injection system and an ignition system. A fuel tank is connected to the injection system of the combustion chamber. The initial conditions of intake, fuel and exhaust are regulated within the three respective tanks, where pressure and temperature are set and monitored using piezoresistive sensors and thermocouples, respectively.

Intake air is supplied by two tanks having a combined volume of 40 L at a pressure of 10 bar. The intake air, tanks, and intake hose are preheated up to 423 K. Under these conditions, the mass flow rate through the valve is choked (up to a pressure of 5.3 bar) [11], reaching 70 g/s at peak cross-section opening. The combustion chamber wall temperature, T_{cc} is a key parameter varied during the experiments. In the reference case, T_{cc} is maintained at 403 K using heat cartridges mounted on the wall. Liquid n-heptane is directly injected into the chamber through a high-pressure gasoline direct injector (Bosch HDEV-2) mounted flush with the wall. This injector is supplied from a 1 L fuel tank pressurized with nitrogen at 100 bar and kept at room temperature. Pressure drop in the air tanks is continuously measured to calculate the overall injected equivalence ratio (OER) of the fresh reactants. Fuel pressure remains constant during the test. The fuel mass flow rate, calibrated in separate dedicated experiments using a scale, is approximately 10 g/s. The chamber is equipped with optical flanges (7980 OF KrF fused silica), providing access to the entire internal rectangle volume for optical diagnostics [11].

The first step involves identifying a range of operating points that ensure a stable cycle sequence using spark ignition. Spark ignition enables a controlled and repeatable ignition timing, serving as a baseline for the analysis. However, in high-frequency cycles, limited mixing and high turbulence lead to misfires [7]. This is where re-ignition becomes advantageous as an ignition mechanism. The conditions under which re-ignition occurs are not yet fully understood, and the current methodology aims to establish operating points that facilitate this phenomenon.

In this study, the fixed test parameters are listed in Table 1, while the varied parameters that were found to promote re-ignition events are detailed in Table 2.

Parameters	Magnitude
Temperature of air tanks	423 [K]
Temperature of air intake tube	423 [K]
Air intake pressure	10 [bar]
N-Heptane Supply Pressure	100 [bar]
Air Intake Valve Timing	0 [ms]
Fuel Injection Timing	9.5 [ms]
Temperature of air tanks	423 [K]
Temperature of air intake tube	423 [K]

Table 1 Parameters kept constant

Influencing Parameters	Range
Initial Pressure	3 - 4 [bar]
Exhaust Pressure (P_{ex})	1 - 2.8 [bar]
Operating frequency	8 - 20 [Hz]
Time Period	50 - 125 [ms]
Intake Valve Opening duration	10 - 11.1 [ms]
Fuel Injection Duration (ER)	4 - 6 [ms]
Ignition Timing	20 - 100 [ms]
Exhaust Valve Timing	5 - 55 [ms]
Exhaust Valve Opening duration	15 - 45 [ms]

Table 2 Influencing parameters varied to obtain different operating points for re-ignition

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Effect of delayed spark ignition on re-ignition

In this section, the facility is operated with a cycle frequency of 8 Hz (hence a period of 125 ms) for a sequence of 20 cycles at stoichiometry. The chamber temperature is set to 403 K for an air intake valve opening duration of 11 ms and fuel injection duration of 6 ms. The exhaust valve timing is set to 55 ms and the exhaust valve duration to 45 ms with the exhaust pressure set to 1 bar. The ignition timings are delayed from 30 ms to 100 ms. A set of 14 tests is done to observe the influence of delayed ignition timing (cf examples on Figure 2).

Figure 2 Example of cycle series in stable spark ignited configuration and re-ignition configuration

The results were analyzed as per successful re-ignition sequences (RIS). A RIS is defined as a sequence where one over two cycles is re-ignited. A RIS success rate p_{RIS} can then be calculated, while omitting the first misfired cycles, to avoid possible incomplete RIS:

$$p_{RIS} = \frac{2R}{R + S}$$

Where R = number of re-ignited cycles and S = number of spark-ignited cycles.

The percentage of RIS obtained for the different cases (Figure 3) are therefore: 0% when all the cycles are spark-ignited, as observed for following ignition timings: 30 to 50 ms and 60 ms; 22 % for a delayed ignition timing of 65 and 70 ms; the RIS increases from the delayed timing of 70 ms until a 100% for a delayed ignition timing of 85 ms is achieved. The RIS then decreases again to 94% for 90 ms and 100 ms delayed ignition timing.

Figure 3 Percentage of re-ignition sequence obtained at different delayed timing

3.2 Characterization of the residual flame intensity

To investigate the occurrence of re-ignition, a case with $p_{RIS} = 100\%$ was examined, using an improved operating frequency of 12.5 Hz over a sequence of 10 cycles. Key parameters included an air intake valve opening duration of 11 ms, a fuel injection duration of 5 ms (Equivalence Ratio: 0.8), an exhaust valve timing of 30 ms, an exhaust valve duration of 30 ms, and an exhaust pressure of 2 bar. The ignition timing was set to 55 ms.

Chemiluminescence images were captured using a high-speed color camera (Phantom V310), enabling differentiation between rich and lean cycles. Additionally, a high-speed black and white camera (Photron SA5) was used to assess quantitative chemiluminescence levels, measured as the total pixel intensity by summing all pixel values in each image.

Figure 4 presents the normalized total pixel intensity of the flame, recorded at a framerate of 3000 fps and a resolution of 256×552 for a spark-ignited cycle (cycle 3) followed by a re-ignited cycle. The integration time was adjusted to capture the low luminosity levels of the spark-ignited flames, causing the camera to saturate during the re-ignition phase of the subsequent cycle. This analysis revealed that re-ignition occurs near the timing of the fuel injection.

Figure 4 Phantom

To further analyze the flame, the chemiluminescence images captured during a spark-ignited cycle (cycle 3) and the subsequent re-ignited cycle (cycle 4), covering the interval from spark ignition to cycle completion, are depicted in Figure 5. Broadband chemiluminescence reveals that the spark-ignited cycle (cycle 3) operates with a partially premixed, fuel-lean mixture, whereas the re-ignited cycle (cycle 4) exhibits a fuel-rich diffusion flame controlled by fuel injection. During re-ignition cycles, fuel is injected directly into a still-burning mixture (corresponding to $t_{ign} + 35$ ms). This is evident from the overall chemiluminescence levels, which remain relatively high when re-ignition occurs, as shown in Figure 5 .

Figure 5 Chemiluminescence images related to spark ignition timing for a spark-ignited cycle (cycle 3) and RI cycle (cycle 4) respectively adapted from Figure 4

4. Conclusion

This research investigates using residual burnt gases as an alternative ignition method for Constant Volume Combustion (CVC). A stable operating point was identified, producing consistent re-ignition events. These re-ignitions, observed over two cycles through chemiluminescence, show that the initial cycle is spark-ignited, leading to a slow flame during the exhaust phase. At the onset of the second cycle, the mixing of fuel and air with the still-burning gases results in the re-ignition of the mixture.

A detailed examination of the decaying residual flame intensity can significantly improve our understanding of the cycle dynamics, thus enhancing the re-ignition process. Interestingly, while chemiluminescence intensity remains high at the cycle's start following a re-ignition, no further re-

ignition takes place under these conditions. This implies that chemiluminescence associated with soot may not reliably indicate the thermo-chemical state needed for re-ignition. Consequently, the final phase of this study will focus on analyzing the sensitivity of p_{RIS} at the point of re-ignition, using integrated and filtered chemiluminescence data for both OH* and CH* emissions. This analysis aims to establish a more accurate predictive criterion for assessing cycle conditions that foster consecutive re-ignition.

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